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Semantic Control Over Neurally Synthesized Audio via Latent Disentanglement

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Abstract

Advances in deep generative models have made it possible to synthesize high-fidelity audio, yet giving users precise, continuous control over the semantic qualities of the generated sound remains challenging. This thesis tackles the problem by combining variational auto-encoders (VAEs) with a latent disentanglement strategy inspired by Fader Networks [1][2]. In this model the encoder learns a compressed latent space invariant to desired control attributes, allowing for precise control over said attributes before the latent representation is passed to the decoder via a "fader" like mechanism. Attributes are computed via a learned linear regression coefficient trained in a supervised manner on continuous attribute labels derived from a synthetic foot-step sound effects dataset. During training, adversarial and reconstruction losses encourage orthogonality between the latent codes and control attributes, ensuring that adjusting one attribute adjusts only the desired content while leaving the rest unchanged. This thesis details the state of the art and core concepts behind the methods used before diving into the details of the implementation. Finally, the results will be presented and discussed.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Recent advancements in generative AI have led to a remarkable surge in creative capabilities, enabling the generation of highly realistic images, text, and audio. These models, trained on vast datasets, can produce novel content that is often indistinguishable from human-created works. In the audio domain, this has resulted in models that can synthesize music in various styles, generate realistic human speech, and create a wide array of sound effects. This progress has opened up exciting possibilities for content creation, music production, and accessibility tools, demonstrating a powerful ability to learn and replicate complex patterns from data.

Despite these impressive capabilities, a significant challenge remains: the lack of fine-grained, intuitive control over the generated output. While users can often guide generation with text prompts or high-level descriptions, controlling specific, continuous attributes, particularly semantic ones like the emotional intensity of a voice or the constituent materials of a sound effect, is often difficult or impossible. The generation process can feel unintuitive, and minor changes to the input can lead to unpredictable or undesirable changes in the output. This gap between the models' generative power and our ability to direct it with precision highlights a crucial area for improvement in generative audio systems.

1.2 Objectives

The goal of this thesis is to take a step towards bridging the gap between the technical domain knowledge needed to produce desired outcomes in audio and the inherent creative potential of people by harnessing the power of AI and generative audio.

While current models can produce impressively realistic audio, they often operate as "black boxes," offering limited, high-level, and often unpredictable controls that are disconnected from the nuanced, technical knowledge of sound designers, musicians, and audio engineers. This work aims to move beyond simple text-prompt-based generation by developing a framework for fine-grained, intuitive control over the fundamental semantic attributes of sound. The goal is to create systems where a user can directly manipulate perceptually relevant qualities, transforming the generative model from a mere content production agent into a responsive and collaborative creative tool.

To achieve this, our research focuses on creating explicit, continuous control mechanisms within the latent space of a state-of-the-art real-time audio generation model [3]. By leveraging techniques like representation learning, adversarial learning, and audio feature embedding, we seek to demonstrate control over certain semantic aspects of audio inputs. This approach builds upon the concept of "fader networks" which allow for the direct and predictable manipulation of attributes within a generated sound or image [1, 2], by extending the scope beyond hand-crafted spectral features and into semantic concepts.

1.3 Structure of the Report

This report is organized into six main chapters.

The second chapter, "Background", establishes the foundational knowledge required to perform this thesis. It begins with an overview of neural network-based audio synthesis and common audio representations. It then delves into the concept of

latent representations and their interpretability, followed by a discussion on audio embeddings, with a specific focus on the principles of contrastive learning and the architecture of the CLAP model.

The third chapter, "VAEs, GANs, RAVE", provides a detailed examination of key generative models relevant to this work. It covers Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), explaining concepts such as marginal likelihood, KL-divergence, and the reparameterization trick. The chapter then discusses Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and the RAVE model, detailing the architecture and training methodologies for each.

The Experiment chapter presents the practical research conducted for this thesis. It introduces the experimental setup and details its design, including the dataset created for the task and the specific model architecture that was implemented and evaluated. After this the results will be evaluated and discussed with regard to their impact and significance, and areas warranting further investigation will be put forward.

Chapter 2

Background

The field of audio generation has seen a significant shift towards deep learning methodologies, moving beyond traditional signal processing and rule-based systems. This evolution mirrors advancements in computer vision and natural language processing, where deep learning facilitates learning representations directly from data. Early neural audio generation integrated neural networks with rule-based systems or used models like Restricted Boltzmann Machines and Deep Belief Networks to predict parameters for frameworks like Hidden Markov Models. The field now encompasses diverse neural architectures including multilayer perceptrons, time-delay neural networks, LSTMs, GRUs, attention-based recurring networks, and mixture density networks.

Neural networks have proven effective in various audio tasks, often outperforming traditional methods with simpler designs and less need for handcrafted features. Training these models requires large, annotated datasets. Inspired by biological auditory systems, deep neural networks with layered structures are used for audio processing, enabling the learning of features at different abstraction levels. Techniques like CNNs, successful in image processing, are also adapted for audio using appropriate representations. The trend in audio generation is towards data-driven approaches where models learn relevant characteristics autonomously.

2.1 Audio Representations

The choice of audio representation is crucial in neural audio systems. Raw audio, while containing all information, is computationally intensive due to high sampling rates and long sequences, and does not directly encode or reveal perceptually relevant information.

Spectrograms, obtained via STFT, offer a time-frequency representation, showing the intensities of the frequency components over time. They are often preferred as they directly contain frequency content important for human hearing and can be treated as image-like data for 2D CNNs.

Other representations include Mel spectrograms which use the Mel scale to align their outputs with human pitch perception, making them effective for tasks involving human listeners.

Researchers often explore alternative representations for specific downstream tasks. Since spectrograms and Mel spectrograms lack phase information for direct playback, neural vocoders are used to synthesize high-quality audio waveforms. Hybrid approaches combining different representations and network architectures also show promise. The selection of representation necessitates a delicate balance between information richness and computational feasibility, with spectral representations often favored over raw audio because of their perceptual relevance and comparably light computational load.

2.2 Latent representations

A latent space is a lower-dimensional, continuous vector space that captures essential features and patterns from training data. Models learn to map high-dimensional input like audio into this compressed space. Points in this space can generate data samples, allowing the model to produce novel data similar to the training data.

VAEs and Transformers use different strategies for latent representations. In VAEs, the encoder maps input to parameters (mean and variance) of a probability distri-

bution (typically Gaussian) in the latent space. This probabilistic approach creates a continuous and smooth latent space, beneficial for diverse outputs and interpolations. The decoder then samples from this distribution to reconstruct data. Transformers, while not explicitly modeling a probabilistic latent space like VAEs, use encoder layers to convert input sequences into fixed-dimensional latent vectors or embeddings. These vectors contain critical information for the decoder to generate output. Some Transformer architectures for conditional generation or style transfer design specific parts of the latent representation to encode particular data attributes. The latent space acts as a compressed, abstract representation, capturing fundamental characteristics without explicitly modeling every detail of raw data. VAEs' probabilistic nature allows varied outputs through sampling, while Transformers' deterministic latent vectors prioritize capturing sequential structure.

Despite advantages, latent space organization and interpretation pose challenges. Interpretability is difficult due to high dimensionality obscuring the relationship between dimensions and human-understandable audio features. Identifying which latent variables control perceptual attributes like timbre or pitch is complex. Achieving disentanglement, where independent data variations are represented by distinct latent space dimensions, is hard; manipulating one dimension often affects multiple output attributes. Establishing causality, understanding how latent space changes cause specific output alterations, is also complex. High dimensionality makes visualization and exploration difficult, limiting intuitive understanding of their structure. This opacity hinders control and understanding of the generation process, limiting the creation of targeted, semantically meaningful audio. Overcoming interpretability and disentanglement challenges is crucial for more user-friendly, controllable generative audio tools.

Dimensionality reduction techniques like PCA and SVD are valuable for analyzing and organizing complex latent spaces. PCA identifies principal components, directions of maximum variance, allowing projection onto lower-dimensional subspaces for visualization while retaining most variance. This helps identify significant variation factors and relationships between latent vectors. SVD, a matrix factorization

technique, reveals underlying structure and relationships in the latent space. Singular values indicate the importance of corresponding singular vectors, allowing focus on the most influential dimensions. While snippets discuss PCA and SVD in image and feature analysis contexts, their principles apply to analyzing latent spaces of audio generative models. Applying PCA or SVD to latent vectors from VAEs or intermediate representations in Transformers can provide insights into latent space organization and primary modes of variation in generated audio. These methods simplify analysis by reducing dimensionality while preserving key information, facilitating better understanding of feature encoding and their contribution to generated audio characteristics.

2.2.1 Interpretability

While generative models offer powerful tools for creating novel data, a significant challenge lies in understanding and controlling their creative process. In theory, the latent space should capture the essential factors of variation in the data, allowing a user to manipulate a latent vector to produce predictable changes in the output. For generative audio, this could mean altering a sound's pitch without changing its timbre, or smoothly transforming a violin into a cello. In practice, however, achieving this level of intuitive control is a difficult and largely unsolved problem.

The primary hurdle is the entangled nature of the learned representations. An ideal latent space would be "disentangled," meaning that individual dimensions in the latent vector would correspond to distinct, interpretable attributes of the output; one for pitch, another for loudness, and so on. However, models rarely learn a clean mapping on their own. Instead, they typically learn entangled representations where a single perceptual feature is encoded across many latent dimensions, and manipulating a single dimension can produce complex and often unpredictable changes to multiple aspects of the sound. This issue is compounded by the difficulty of even measuring disentanglement. Research has shown that existing metrics for evaluating the quality of disentangled representations are often unreliable and do not necessarily correlate with downstream task performance or genuine interpretability, making

it difficult to objectively assess whether a model has learned a useful structure.

Even if a latent space is interpretable, navigating it to create meaningful transformations is not straightforward. The most obvious approach, linear interpolation between two points in the latent space, often fails to produce a perceptually smooth transition, due to uncertainty as to whether or not the path moves through realistic outputs. For audio, this can result in a series of muffled, noisy, or perceptually implausible sounds during a transformation. This problem highlights that the geometry of the latent space is rarely simple or understandable. To generate a sequence of valid intermediate samples in the latent space of a VAE for example, one must find a path that remains within high-probability regions of the learned distribution.

Two common approaches to latent space disentanglement for generative models include β -VAE and InfoGAN. The β -VAE introduces a hyperparameter β to the standard VAE objective, encouraging the latent distribution to closely match a factorized prior and thus disentangle independent factors of variation. By penalizing the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence more heavily, β -VAEs can learn latent spaces where single dimensions correspond to interpretable attributes. However, if the β term is too large the increased interpretability may come at the cost of reduced reconstruction fidelity [4]. InfoGAN, on the other hand, augments the GAN objective with an information-theoretic regularizer to maximize mutual information between a subset of the latent space and the data, enabling the recovery of interpretable, disentangled factors in an unsupervised manner [5].

Building on these techniques, FactorVAE explicitly encourages independence among latent dimensions by penalizing the "total correlation," a statistical measure of redundancy among random variables. FactorVAE achieves a superior trade-off between disentanglement and reconstruction quality compared to β -VAE, but requires an auxiliary discriminator to estimate total correlation, introducing additional complexity to training [6]. Further innovations such as β -TCVAE and DIP-VAE propose refined regularizations or posteriors, addressing some of the stability and complexity issues present in earlier models. Recent work also questions the reliability of disentanglement metrics, highlighting that even high-scoring models may not guarantee

meaningful or consistent control over generative factors, particularly in complex domains like audio [5]. Thus, while current approaches like β -VAE, InfoGAN, and FactorVAE have significantly advanced the disentanglement of latent spaces, open challenges remain in balancing interpretability, generative quality, and reliable evaluation.

Fader Networks

Fader Networks aim for controllable generation by learning a latent space where dimensions correspond to semantically meaningful attributes. The concept involves training a generative model such that traversing a specific latent space direction or dimension results in a continuous, predictable change in a particular output attribute (e.g., brightness, style, timbre) while others remain unaffected [1]. This is achieved through an adversarial approach whereby a discriminator network attempts to predict certain features by inspecting the latent space itself. The goal of the model’s encoder is to learn a representation invariant to these features, meaning the encoder ignores them, in order to fool the discriminator. The true feature values are then appended to the latent space, and decoded to produce outputs. This adversarial aspect allows the user to pinpoint exactly which dimension corresponds to the desired control attributes, allowing for controllable generation with regard to the chosen features [1]. F-RAVE, an extension of the generative audio model RAVE, builds upon this concept by learning a mapping between continuous, human-understandable audio descriptors (e.g., spectral centroid for brightness, RMS for loudness) and the latent space of a generative model [2]. This enables finer, more intuitive control over generated sound by directly manipulating these descriptors. The idea behind Fader Networks builds on the broader goal of creating a well-organized latent space where different data aspects are encoded in a disentangled way. Fader Networks offer a promising approach to making generative audio models more controllable and user-friendly by providing intuitive ways to manipulate specific sound characteristics. Their development highlights the increasing demand for more interpretable and controllable generative models in audio, moving beyond realistic sound generation to precise artistic expression and manipulation.

2.3 Audio embeddings

Audio embedding is a technique in machine learning that transforms complex audio signals into compact, low-dimensional numerical vector representations [7]. Raw audio, whether as a time-domain waveform or a high-resolution spectrogram, is inherently high-dimensional and difficult for many algorithms to process directly. The primary goal of an embedding is to distill the perceptually and structurally important characteristics of a sound—such as its timbral qualities, pitch contours, and rhythmic patterns—into a dense and meaningful representation [8]. This not only makes the data more computationally tractable but also creates a structured feature space where sounds with similar acoustic properties are positioned closely together, enabling tasks like similarity-based retrieval, classification, and manipulation for creative applications. These embeddings are most commonly learned using deep neural networks, particularly models with an autoencoder architecture. In this framework, an encoder network learns to compress an input audio segment into a compact latent vector—the embedding itself—while a corresponding decoder network learns to reconstruct the original audio from only this vector.

Other popular approaches learn embeddings through different objectives. Self-supervised models like Wav2Vec 2.0 operate directly on raw waveforms, learning rich features by predicting masked or missing portions of the audio signal. Another common strategy involves transfer learning, where models like VGGish first convert audio into a spectrogram—a visual representation—and then process this image with a convolutional neural network originally designed for computer vision tasks [9]. Finally, multimodal models such as CLAP use contrastive learning to create a shared embedding space between audio and text, learning to align sounds with their corresponding descriptions [10].

2.3.1 Contrastive Learning

Contrastive learning is a machine learning paradigm in which a model learns to distinguish between similar and dissimilar data points. The core idea is to learn an

embedding space where "positive pairs" (similar items) are brought closer together, while "negative pairs" (dissimilar items) are pushed further apart. For any given data point, referred to as the "anchor," a positive sample is a related item (e.g., an augmented version of the same image), and negative samples are all other items in a training batch [8]. By optimizing a contrastive loss function, the model learns to produce representations that cluster semantically similar items without needing explicit, human-provided labels for every single class.

OpenAI's CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training) model applies this principle to bridge the gap between vision and text. CLIP utilizes a dual-encoder architecture: one encoder processes images, and another processes text descriptions. During its pre-training phase, the model is fed a massive dataset of (image, text) pairs collected from the internet. For each pair, the image and its corresponding text form a positive pair, while the image and the text from all other pairs in the batch are treated as negative pairs. The model's objective is to maximize the cosine similarity of the embeddings for the correct image-text pairs while minimizing it for all incorrect pairs. This process effectively aligns the two modalities into a single, shared embedding space [11].

This same contrastive methodology has been successfully extended to the audio domain with models like CLAP (Contrastive Language-Audio Pre-training). CLAP learns a joint embedding space that aligns sounds with their corresponding text descriptions. By training on pairs of audio clips and their textual metadata, CLAP can perform zero-shot audio classification, identifying sounds based on natural language queries (e.g., "a dog barking" or "a car horn"). This cross-modal capability is crucial for applications like audio retrieval, where users can search vast sound libraries using descriptive text rather than other audio examples [10].

Chapter 3

VAEs, GANs, and RAVE

This chapter will introduce and explain Variational Autoencoders (VAEs), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and the RAVE model.

3.1 Variational Autoencoders

Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) constitute a class of generative neural networks that transcend conventional autoencoder limitations by incorporating probabilistic modeling principles. Unlike traditional autoencoders that produce deterministic latent representations, VAEs encode input data as probability distributions within a continuous latent space, enabling the generation of novel data samples that maintain structural fidelity to the training distribution. This probabilistic framework, originally formulated by Kingma and Welling in 2013, revolutionized generative modeling by providing a mathematically principled approach to generation while somewhat preserving the interpretability and controllability of the learned representations [12].

VAEs are comprised of an encoder network that maps input observations to distributional parameters (mean and variance) in a latent space, a stochastic sampling mechanism facilitated by the reparameterization trick, and a decoder network that reconstructs data from sampled latent vectors. The model optimizes a composite objective function that balances reconstruction fidelity against regularization con-

straints, specifically minimizing the Kullback-Leibler divergence between the learned posterior distribution and a specified prior distribution. This dual optimization creates a structured latent manifold where semantically similar inputs cluster together, facilitating meaningful interpolation and controlled generation through latent space manipulation [12].

VAEs demonstrate exceptional utility in research applications requiring both data compression and generation capabilities, offering superior training stability compared to adversarial approaches while maintaining theoretical grounding in variational inference principles. The structured latent space facilitates rigorous analysis of model behavior while the generative capabilities enable comprehensive evaluation across diverse scenarios.

3.1.1 Marginal Likelihood

The mathematical foundation of VAEs rests on the intractable marginal likelihood problem. Given observed data \mathbf{x} and latent variables \mathbf{z} , we seek to maximize the marginal likelihood $p_\theta(\mathbf{x}) = \int p_\theta(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z})p_\theta(\mathbf{z})d\mathbf{z}$, where θ represents the parameters of our generative model. Since this integral is computationally intractable for machine learning models, VAEs introduce an approximate posterior $q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$ parameterized by ϕ , typically implemented as a neural network encoder. The key insight lies in deriving a tractable lower bound on the log marginal likelihood through Jensen’s inequality, yielding the Evidence Lower Bound (ELBO):

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \phi; \mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{E}q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})[\log p_\theta(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{z})] - D_{KL}(q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})\|p_\theta(\mathbf{z}))$$

This formula decomposes the objective into two components: a reconstruction term that ensures the decoder can accurately reconstruct inputs from latent representations, and a regularization term that constrains the approximate posterior to align with the specified prior distribution [12].

3.1.2 KL-Divergence

The Kullback-Leibler divergence serves as a fundamental measure that quantifies the dissimilarity between two probability distributions, functioning as a crucial regularization mechanism in VAEs that prevents posterior collapse and ensures meaningful latent space structure [12]. Mathematically defined as $D_{KL}(P\|Q) = \mathbb{E}_x \sim P[\log P(x) - \log Q(x)]$ for continuous distributions, the KL divergence is asymmetric and always non-negative, reaching zero only when the distributions are identical. In the VAE framework, $DKL(q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})\|p(\mathbf{z}))$ specifically measures how the learned approximate posterior deviates from the specified prior distribution, typically a standard multivariate Gaussian $\mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$. When both distributions are Gaussian, this divergence admits a closed-form solution: $D_{KL} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^J (1 + \log(\sigma_j^2) - \mu_j^2 - \sigma_j^2)$, where J represents the latent dimensionality [12]. This regularization term prevents the encoder from learning arbitrarily complex posterior distributions that would overfit to the training data, instead encouraging the latent space to maintain continuity and structure essential for interpolation and generation. The balance between reconstruction accuracy and KL regularization creates a natural trade-off that shapes the learned representations, with higher KL weights promoting more structured but potentially less expressive latent spaces, while lower weights risk posterior collapse where latent variables become uninformative.

3.1.3 Reparameterization Trick

The critical innovation enabling end-to-end optimization lies in the reparameterization trick, which transforms the stochastic sampling operation into a differentiable function. Rather than directly sampling from $q_\phi(\mathbf{z}|\mathbf{x})$, VAEs reparameterize the latent variable as

$$\mathbf{z} = \boldsymbol{\mu}\phi(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\sigma}\phi(\mathbf{x}) \odot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$$

, where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{I})$ represents auxiliary noise independent of the model parameters, and \odot denotes element-wise multiplication. This transformation allows gradients to flow through the sampling process, enabling standard backpropagation while main-

taining the stochastic nature essential for regularization and generation [12]. The mathematical elegance of this approach provides VAEs with superior training stability compared to adversarial methods while preserving the theoretical guarantees of variational inference, making them particularly suitable for research applications requiring both interpretable latent representations and reliable generative capabilities.

Figure 1: A visual depiction of a typical VAE architecture. The encoder takes the input data and compresses it into a latent representation, typically via a series of convolutional layers. The decoder then decompresses this representation and seeks to produce a perceptually identical output.

3.1.4 Conditioning VAEs

Conditional Variational Autoencoders (cVAEs) extend standard VAEs by introducing side information or labels (often denoted as y) into both the encoder and decoder networks, enabling controllable and structured generation. As described in a detailed in an academic overview of conditioning in VAEs [13], the conditioning variable can represent a wide range of semantic concepts such as class, style, or any structured language-based attribute you wish the model to learn and generate.

There are two principal approaches to incorporating conditioning: assuming the latent variable z and the conditioning variable y are independent, or making them dependent.

In the independent case, the prior for z and y factorizes as $p(z, y) = p(z)p(y)$, which

promotes disentangled representations. This is desirable for tasks where you want z to capture "everything except" the information in y , making the generative model more controllable (e.g. Fader Networks) [13].

Alternatively, the dependent case sets a conditional prior $p(z|y)p(y)$, often resulting in a more expressive model but with less independent control over each source of variation.

The cVAE's objective function encourages the learned posterior $q(z|x, y)$ to approximate the specified (potentially conditional) prior, while the decoder $p(x|z, y)$ reconstructs the data from both z and y .

Tuning the regularization term (i.e., the weight on the KL divergence) is critical: if it's too low, the latent variable may "leak" information about y , making the conditioning ineffective; if it's too high, the model's generation quality degrades due to the forced independence or matching to a too-simple prior.

The discussion also highlights that the independent cVAE formulation is particularly suitable for controllable generation (like swapping semantic attributes), while the dependent variant is often more powerful for conditional data modeling. Ultimately, the chosen conditioning strategy depends on the desired trade-off between interpretability/controllability, and the quality of the generation [13].

3.2 Generative Adversarial Networks

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) introduce a method of deep learning that pits two neural networks against each other. The approach mimics an adversarial game between a counterfeiter and a detective, with one network generating synthetic data while the other tries to detect it [14].

The framework operates on a simple principle. The generator network creates synthetic samples that resemble real training data, and the discriminator network evaluates these samples and determines their authenticity. Through this competition, both networks improve their performance [14]. The generator becomes better at

creating realistic data, while the discriminator becomes more skilled at detection.

This adversarial training process produces remarkable results. GANs can generate images, text, audio, and other data types that humans often cannot distinguish from real examples. The applications span numerous fields, from computer vision to natural language processing. The mathematical foundation builds on game theory. The generator and discriminator engage in a minmax game, where each network tries to optimize its objective function. The generator minimizes the discriminator’s ability to classify its outputs as fake. The discriminator maximizes its classification accuracy between real and generated samples.

3.2.1 Architecture

The GAN architecture for audio generation employs the same fundamental adversarial principle as image generation but adapts to the unique challenges of temporal data. The generator network typically receives random noise as input and transforms it into coherent audio sequences, though this differs in the RAVE approach as will be discussed later.

The discriminator architecture often mirrors the generator design but in reverse. Raw waveform discriminators use one-dimensional convolutions with stride to reduce temporal dimensions while extracting increasingly abstract features as data propagates through neural network layers. The network processes audio sequences through multiple layers, each detecting patterns at different time scales. After producing a compressed, high-level feature representation through this process, the final layer completes the classification task by producing a single probability that indicates whether the input represents real or generated audio.

3.2.2 Training

During each training step, the two networks optimise separate but coupled loss functions that form a mini-max game 1. The discriminator loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_D = -[\log D(x) + \log(1 - D(G(z)))]$$

Where $D(x)$ is the discriminator's prediction based on the real data and $D(G(z))$ is the prediction based on the fake data.

It is computed while the generator's weights are frozen. Back-propagation adjusts only the discriminator so that real samples x are pushed toward $D(x)=1$ and synthetic samples $G(z)$ toward $D(G(z))=0$. The generator loss is as follows:

$$L_G = -\log D(G(z)) \tag{3.1}$$

In this phase the discriminator's weights are frozen, the loss is back-propagated through the discriminator into the generator, and only the generator's parameters are updated. This pushes $D(G(z))$ upward, encouraging the generator to produce outputs that the current discriminator cannot reject. Alternating these two gradient updates keeps the game balanced: the discriminator learns to sharpen its decision boundary while the generator learns to shift the synthetic data distribution toward the real one. Training continues until neither network can significantly reduce its own loss, an empirical sign that the model has reached the Nash equilibrium defined in the original GAN paper [14].

3.3 RAVE

Realtime Audio Variational autoEncoder (RAVE) offers a powerful approach to neural audio generation which harnesses the representational power of VAEs while mitigating the "blurriness" of their outputs by introducing GAN upsampling. It learns a smooth, low-latency latent space during an initial VAE phase and later sharpens the decoded waveforms with adversarial fine-tuning. The result is a single model that (i) runs more than twenty times faster than real time on a laptop CPU, (ii) reconstructs or transforms full-band 48 kHz audio, and (iii) exposes a compact latent vector that musicians can modulate in real time [3].

Figure 2: A visual depiction of a typical GAN architecture. The generator creates fake data from a compressed latent representation, and the discriminator performs the reverse process (downsampling) in order to understand and discern between real and fake data.

3.3.1 Architecture

RAVE follows an encoder–decoder layout. Both sides use 1-D convolutions but operate in eight parallel sub-bands obtained with a Pseudo-Quadrature Mirror Filter (PQMF). Working on sub-bands reduces the temporal footprint of each convolution and lowers latency.

Encoder: five strided convolution blocks downsample the time resolution at each layer and upsample the channel count, providing a compressed latent vector per frame. Batch normalization and leaky-ReLU keep gradients stable.

Latent layer: the VAE structure allows for variational sampling from the latent representation via regularization towards standard normal prior during the training stage. Post-training PCA lets the user trade reconstruction fidelity for lower bitrate by retaining fewer principal components.

Decoder: five transposed convolution blocks mirror the encoder. Skip connections pass fine details around the bottleneck. A lightweight noise synthesizer adds high-

frequency residuals that the main path may miss.

Discriminator (training only): a multi-scale spectral discriminator, adapted from EnCodec, judges the realism of reconstructed waveforms at three temporal resolutions. The entire network remains fully convolutional and non-causal during training but can switch to cached causal convolutions at export, yielding end-to-end latencies well below 20 ms.

3.3.2 Training

RAVE trains in two stages.

Representation learning (VAE phase):

The model sees fixed-length waveform excerpts (and minimizes the standard evidence lower bound:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \|x - \hat{x}\|_1 + \beta \text{KL}(q(z | x) \| \mathcal{N}(0, 1)) \quad (3.2)$$

The loss two ingredients:

Reconstruction term – measures how different the decoded audio is from the original clip. Smaller differences mean the model is reconstructing the sound more faithfully.

Regularisation term – nudges the hidden (latent) variables to follow a simple bell-curve distribution. This keeps the latent space smooth and easy to explore. A weighting factor β balances these two goals: accurate playback versus a tidy, well-behaved latent space.

with $\beta = 1$ during the first 200 k batches. Adam (learning rate 2×10^{-4} , $\beta_1 = 0.5$, $\beta_2 = 0.9$) updates all weights. This stage yields a smooth latent manifold and a decent, albeit slightly muffled, output.

Adversarial fine-tuning.

After the latent space has converged, the Kullback–Leibler term is frozen. Training then switches to a hinge-loss GAN objective:

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} + \lambda_{\text{FM}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{FM}} - \lambda_{\text{adv}} \mathbb{E}[D(\hat{x})], \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_D = \mathbb{E}[\max(0, 1 - D(x))] + \mathbb{E}[\max(0, 1 + D(\hat{x}))]. \quad (3.4)$$

Feature matching \mathcal{L}_{FM} aligns intermediate discriminator activations and stabilises training. The discriminator learns three times faster than the generator (learning rate 4×10^{-4} vs. 1.3×10^{-4}) to prevent mode collapse. Fine-tuning runs for 600 k steps, after which the model reaches 48 kHz fidelity while still decoding 128-sample hops in under 1 ms on a CPU [3].

The adversarial fine-tuning stage essentially addresses the perceptual shortcomings of the variational autoencoder stage. While the VAE objective ensures stable training and broad coverage of the data distribution, it often produces outputs that sound overly smooth or lacking in the rich high-frequency detail crucial for realistic audio. By introducing a GAN-based hinge-loss objective after the latent space has already converged, RAVE forces the generator to produce outputs that a discriminator cannot distinguish from real signals. This adversarial feedback sharpens transients, restores crispness in the spectral envelope, and closes the perceptual gap between reconstructions and natural audio recordings. The feature matching term further stabilizes this adversarial interplay by anchoring the generator’s updates to the intermediate activations of the discriminator, encouraging consistency rather than pure adversarial fooling.

One of the key innovations in this phase is the careful calibration of learning rates and update schedules between the generator and discriminator. By making the discriminator learn roughly three times faster, the system prevents the generator from collapsing into trivial strategies that minimize reconstruction loss without capturing authentic variation in the data. The explicit design of the hinge GAN loss also miti-

gates issues of vanishing gradients, ensuring that the discriminator continues to provide useful training signals even after long optimization runs. Crucially, adversarial fine-tuning is not performed indefinitely; after around 600k steps, the improvements saturate, yielding a balance between naturalness and computational efficiency, allowing for high-fidelity (48 kHz) generation while maintaining sub-millisecond decoding on CPUs.

Beyond raw fidelity, the adversarial stage also broadens the robustness of the model. Augmentations like gain modulation, dynamic range compression, and silent dropout force the generator to handle variations often seen in the real world. The final tensor-based pruning step is made possible by the structure that emerges during adversarial training: not every latent axis contributes equally to fooling the discriminator, so identifying and discarding the unused ones enables lightweight versions of the model without sacrificing perceptual quality. In effect, adversarial fine-tuning transforms the VAE’s “coarse but stable” representation into a compact and expressive synthesis engine that rivals human-audible fidelity.

Chapter 4

Experiment

To address the challenge of limited controllability in generative audio, this chapter presents an experiment focused on achieving semantic attribute control through the disentanglement of a RAVE-based model’s latent space. The central hypothesis is that by leveraging a dataset with explicit, continuous attribute labels, we can disentangle the latent representation through adversarial learning, thereby confidently mapping certain dimensions to desired control attributes and enabling fine-grained control. This experiment details the implementation of a method to effectively create one or more "semantic faders" capable of manipulating perceptual qualities like walking speed or surface material. The following sections will outline the experimental design, the creation of a purpose-built dataset, and the specific architecture of the model used.

4.1 Experiment design

In order to assess the model’s capability to disentangle its latent space and allocate certain dimensions to desired control attributes, we trained the model on synthesized footsteps dataset and aimed for disentanglement of two semantic features: "grassiness" and "speed".

4.1.1 Dataset

To facilitate the training of a controllable generative system, a specialized dataset was created consisting of 4 hours of synthesized footstep audio clips. This dataset was purpose-built to provide clean, continuous, attribute labels essential for concept-aware vectors for generalizable attribute detection in footstep audio samples [15]. Each audio clip is associated with four specific floating-point values that define its perceptual characteristics: 'speed', 'grass', 'wood', and 'concrete'. 'Grass', 'wood', and 'concrete' refer to the degree to which each respective material is present on the ground upon which the footsteps land. For the purposes of this experiment, we passed two attributes to the model in the hopes of achieving disentanglement: "grassiness" and "speed". By using synthesized audio, we ensure that these attribute values represent a ground truth, allowing us to confidently train the latent discriminator without worrying about overly noisy attribute data.

The dataset's structure was systematically designed to cover a wide range of attribute combinations, allowing the model to observe how changes in each parameter independently affect the resulting sound. The continuous nature of the labels is particularly crucial, as it enables the use of regression-based techniques to identify a coefficient vector capable of producing an attribute score when combined with an audio embedding vector. With 2401 unique samples, the dataset provides sufficient density and variety to train a model that can robustly map these semantic concepts to specific, controllable dimensions in the latent space, forming the foundation for the "semantic fader" control system investigated in this experiment.

4.1.2 Embedding and Attribute Computation

The core of this project's approach to attribute control lies in translating abstract, human-understandable concepts like "speed" or "grassiness" into concrete mathematical directions within a model's latent space. To achieve this, we compute concept vectors for each desired semantic attribute. This method is inspired by the foundational work on Concept Activation Vectors (CAV) by Kim et al [16]. While

their work originally used linear classifiers to distinguish the presence or absence of a concept for interpretability, this project adapts the core idea for a generative purpose. Instead of a binary classification, we treat the task as a continuous regression problem, which is better suited for the smoothly varying attributes in our synthesized audio dataset.

The specific technique employed here is what we term a Regression Concept Vector (RCV). For each attribute (e.g., speed, grassiness), a separate linear regression model is trained. This model learns to predict the continuous ground-truth value of the attribute (e.g., a float from 0.0 to 1.0) directly from the high-dimensional latent space embeddings produced by the CLAP model. The key insight is that the learned coefficient vector of this linear regressor represents the direction in the latent space of the CLAP model that corresponds most strongly to an increase in that specific attribute's value. This vector and its ability to predict semantic attributes provides the basis for the disentanglement of the downstream VAE's latent representation.

This regression-based approach for steering generative models aligns with a broader research effort into creating more disentangled and controllable representations. By framing concept-to-vector mapping as a regression task, we can directly leverage labeled data to create controls that are not just representative of whether or not an attribute is present in data but also exhibit to what degree the attribute is present. This allows for a more intuitive and powerful method of "steering" the generative process.

This RCV is not used to manipulate the CLAP space directly. Instead it serves as a crucial tool for structuring the latent space of the core generative model. The RCV's ability to produce a scalar attribute score from an audio embedding provides the quantitative basis for the adversarial disentanglement of the downstream VAE's latent representation. In the main training loop, the latent discriminator is tasked with predicting these attribute scores from the VAE encoder's output. The encoder, in turn, is trained to produce a latent code that "fools" the discriminator, thereby learning a representation that is explicitly invariant to—or disentangled from—the attribute in question. This allows the ground-truth attribute value to be appended

later as a conditional input to the decoder, facilitating precise and independent control.

4.1.3 Audio Representation

The choice of audio representation as input to the VAE model is crucial and has a great impact on the model’s outcomes. We decided to convert the raw WAV files to a 16-band Pseudo-Quadrature Mirror Filter (PQMF) bank, a specialized digital signal processing tool used to efficiently decompose a single, high-bandwidth signal into multiple, lower-bandwidth sub-band signals [17].

The core of the PQMF system is an analysis filter bank, which takes the input audio and passes it through a series of parallel band-pass filters. Each filter is designed to isolate a specific frequency range. After filtering, the signal in each sub-band is downsampled. Because each sub-band now contains a much narrower range of frequencies, its sampling rate can be significantly reduced without losing information, a process known as critical sampling. This decomposition is highly efficient as it reduces the temporal resolution and computational load required to process audio data in subsequent steps [17].

Figure 3: Overview of the PQMF architecture

The main VAE model is tasked with taking in this PQMF representation and providing a faithful reconstruction. To get back to the original audio, the sub-band

signals are fed into a corresponding synthesis filter bank. First, each sub-band signal is upsampled by inserting zeros between the existing samples to return it to the original sampling rate. Then, each upsampled signal is passed through a synthesis filter that mirrors the properties of its corresponding analysis filter. The outputs from all the synthesis filters are then summed together to produce a replica of the original full-bandwidth signal.

We chose this representation due to its effectiveness in making the computationally expensive task of processing raw audio more tractable by representing the audio as a collection of multiple frequency bands, and its ability to achieve a near-perfect reconstruction of the original signal [17].

Instead of forcing the VAE to learn the intricate structure of the full-bandwidth audio at once, the PQMF splits the signal into multiple lower-frequency sub-bands. This decomposition significantly reduces the temporal resolution that the encoder and decoder must process within each band, making the learning task computationally more efficient and stable. Furthermore, since the reconstruction loss is calculated directly on these perceptually relevant sub-bands, the model is optimized to minimize errors in distinct frequency ranges, which often leads to higher-fidelity audio synthesis. The near-perfect reconstruction property of the PQMF ensures that the audio quality is preserved during the encoding and decoding stages, allowing the model to focus entirely on the generative task without introducing artifacts.

4.1.4 Model Architecture

The model is a conditional Variational Autoencoder (VAE) enhanced with an adversarial component. The core of the model consists of an encoder, which compresses the multi-band audio into a lower-dimensional latent space, and a conditional decoder, which reconstructs the audio from a sample of this latent space combined with explicit attribute information.

The VAE’s architecture is defined by a symmetric encoder-decoder structure operating on a 16-band PQMF representation of the audio. The Encoder is a deep

convolutional network that progressively downsamples the input through four main blocks with temporal downsampling ratios of [4, 4, 4, 2]. This compresses the temporal dimensionality of the input audio by a factor of 128. The decoder mirrors this architecture, using four corresponding upsampling blocks to reconstruct the 16-band audio from a latent vector. Importantly, the decoder is conditional: its input is a 130-dimensional vector created by concatenating the 128-dimensional latent code with a 2-dimensional attribute vector (speed and grassiness), enabling controlled synthesis.

Several key hyperparameters govern the model’s training and behavior. The latent space has a dimensionality of 128, providing a compact representation of the audio features. The VAE loss function is balanced by a term weighting the KL divergence, which is set to 0.2 during the training step. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 1e-3 and a batch size of 16. Audio inputs are processed as 6-second clips sampled at 44.1 kHz.

The training process uses a hybrid objective function that combines classic VAE losses with an adversarial loss. The VAE is trained to minimize a reconstruction loss, which is calculated as a multi-scale spectral distance between the original and generated audio sub-bands to ensure perceptual similarity. Alongside this, a Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence loss regularizes the encoder, pushing the distribution of the latent space to approximate a standard gaussian prior distribution. This regularization is crucial for ensuring that the latent space is smooth and continuous, allowing for meaningful interpolation and generation of novel audio samples.

Latent discriminator

The adversarial component introduces a unique dynamic to the training. A ‘latent discriminator’ is trained concurrently to predict the audio’s descriptive attributes directly from the latent code produced by the encoder. The discriminator is rewarded for making correct predictions and the encoder is rewarded for fooling the discriminator. This adversarial objective forces the encoder to learn a disentangled latent representation where specific dimensions correlate with the audio attributes.

The decoder then leverages this structured latent code along with the ground-truth attributes to perform conditional synthesis, enabling control over the characteristics of the generated audio.

The architecture of the discriminator consists of two main parts: a shared feature extraction backbone followed by attribute-specific prediction heads. The input to the model is the latent code 'z'. The shared feature extraction stage begins with a series of blocks, each containing a 1d convolutional layer with a kernel size of 7, followed by batch normalization and a LeakyReLU activation. These initial layers process the latent sequence while maintaining its channel dimension. After these repeating blocks, an additional convolutional block reduces the channel dimension by half. This shared representation is then fed into a separate prediction head for each attribute. Each head further refines the features, first with a convolutional block that reduces channels to 32, and then with a final convolutional layer that acts as the classifier, mapping the 32-channel representation to an output with output channels equalling the number of quantization bins. This final output contains the raw logits for each quantized bin for every time step in the sequence. This discriminator approach mirrors the one used by Devis et al. in their 2023 paper [2].

Attribute computation and prediction

The computed semantic attributes are stored as a vector of length equal to the temporal dimensionality of the input audio's latent representation to allow for appending before being passed to the decoder.

Before model training, quantization bins are computed on the entire dataset by mapping the set of continuous attribute values to a discrete set, enabling the discriminator to handle attribute computation as a classification problem. All attribute vectors are quantized into 16 bins to match the output of the latent discriminator. The accuracy of the discriminator is then assessed by cross-entropy loss.

Quantization is the process of mapping a large, continuous set of values into a smaller, discrete set, often referred to as bins. In models like F-RAVE, which deal with continuous attribute prediction, quantization enables the model to handle at-

tribute prediction as a classification problem by assigning continuous predictions to a finite number of bins.

In this implementation, quantization was done by continuous feature values (scaling them to the range $[-1, 1]$), sorts these values, and then defining bin thresholds by selecting equidistant indices across the sorted data, effectively dividing the attribute range into 16 bins.

The latent discriminator predicted attributes via logit computation across all 16 attribute bins. Cross-entropy loss was then computed between the real and predicted attribute values. Formally, cross-entropy loss is defined as

$$L = - \sum_{k=1}^K y_k \log(p_k)$$

where K is the number of classes, y_k is the true label, and p_k is the predicted probability for class k .

Chapter 5

Results

This chapter will exhibit the results of the experiment detailed in the previous chapter, beginning with the performance of the attribute computation method and moving to the perceptual results of modifying the latent axes corresponding to the disentangled semantic attributes.

5.1 Attribute Computation

5.1.1 Speed

The RCV dedicated to speed (Fig. 4-1) achieves an R^2 of 0.990 on the training data and 0.984 on the unseen test clips, indicating that the learned regression coefficient is highly predictive of footstep tempo.

5.1.2 Surface Material Attributes

While performance stays solid for the "grassiness" attribute ($R^2 = 0.988$), prediction quality drops markedly for the two other "material" dimensions: Upon perceptual evaluation of the dataset, this is likely due to a high level of entanglement between "grassiness" and the other material attributes. For example, adding "woodiness" to a clip with high "grassiness" resulted in much less of a perceptual difference

than performing the inverse operation. Due to this entanglement, only "speed" and "grassiness" were chosen as perceptual attributes to disentangle during training.

5.1.3 Plots

Figures 4-1 to 4-4 summarize the quality with which the learned regression-concept vectors (RCVs) recover the four continuous attributes encoded in the foot-step dataset. Each panel shows the predicted value against the ground-truth value for the test set; the dashed red line indicates perfect prediction. The coefficient of determination (R^2) obtained from the full linear regressor are annotated in each plot

Figure 4: These four plots show test performance of the learned RCV for each of the considered semantic attributes in this experiment. The "speed" and "grassiness" RCVs perform well, while the other attributes are harder to predict.

5.2 Semantic Fader Model

This section will detail the quantitative and perceptual results related to training and inference of the proposed VAE/GAN generative audio model on the synthesized footsteps dataset.

Latent Size	Ratios	N PQMF Bands	Num Bins
128	[4, 4, 4, 2]	16	16

Table 1: Model configuration of the most successful training run. "Latent Size" refers to the number of dimensions present in the model's latent representation. "Ratios" refers to the downsampling/upsampling ratio at each convolutional layer of the encoder/decoder. The product of these ratios gives the total sampling factor = 128. "N PQMF Bands" refers to the amount of frequency sub-bands the audio was decomposed into as input to the model. "Num Bins" refers to the amount of bins used to quantize the continuous attributes.

5.2.1 Reconstruction Fidelity

Reconstruction fidelity was measured via a multi-scale spectral distance computed on PQMF sub-bands. Given the multiband signals $x_{\text{mb}}, y_{\text{mb}} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times C \times T}$, we apply magnitude STFTs at scales $\mathcal{S} = \{2048, 1024, 512, 256, 128\}$ with hop $s/4$ to each band and aggregate across bands and scales. At each scale s , the distance couples a relative L2 term on linear magnitudes with an L1 term on log-magnitudes (stabilized by $\varepsilon = 10^{-7}$), encouraging both envelope matching and contrast at different loudness levels. The formal definition is given below:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{recon}}(x, y) = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \left(\frac{\| |X_s| - |Y_s| \|_2}{\| |X_s| \|_2} + \| \log(|X_s| + \varepsilon) - \log(|Y_s| + \varepsilon) \|_1 \right),$$

where $X_s = \text{STFT}_s(x_{\text{mb}})$ and $Y_s = \text{STFT}_s(y_{\text{mb}})$. The loss is computed per PQMF band (by reshaping bands into the batch) and summed over scales, yielding the scalar `spectral_distance` used for training loss.

The reconstruction loss curve in figure 5 exhibits a rapid initial decrease followed by a slower, steady improvement, converging near a stable regime after roughly the mid-training stage. Listening tests indicated strong preservation of overall "shape" and amplitude envelope, but comparatively less high-frequency and fine-grained

Figure 5: Reconstruction loss over roughly 750,000 training steps

temporal detail (e.g., sharp transients and subtle textures). This gap likely reflects the inability of VAEs alone to generate highly faithful reconstructions due to KL-divergence regulation enforcing a smooth latent space, resulting in "blurry" outputs.

5.2.2 Quantitative Evaluation

The performance of the attribute control mechanism was evaluated by applying the aforementioned RCV attribute computation strategy to both auto-encoded audio without any alterations to the disentangled latent dimensions and its their outputs with added bias.

Scores were computed by averaging RCV-CLAP embedding dot products among all examples with a particular attribute score (for original audio clips) or a particular attribute bias. The scores for all biased outputs are shown relative to the original clip, adding a bias being the only change.

Figures 6 and 7 display the results of the evaluation. Attribute manipulations were done by adding a bias (constant float) to the disentangled dimension in the latent representation of the encoded audio. The figures show that, on average, adding a bias resulted in quantitatively higher predicted attribute scores. Figure 6 shows

that adding a bias of 0.75 to the speed dimension resulted in an increased predicted speed score of approximately 0.4. Figure 7 shows that biasing the grass dimension of audio clips with no grass presence results in marked increased in the predicted grass score of the auto-encoded files.

Interestingly, biasing each attribute did result in increased scores for the other attribute. It is worthwhile to note that biasing a dimension by a certain amount did not result in consistent score predictions equal to (original score + bias), however it is clear that adding to a disentangled dimension results in an increase in qualitative measures of the presence of the corresponding attribute.

Figure 6: Computed speed for original and auto-encoded audio clips

Figure 7: Computed grassiness for original and auto-encoded audio clips

5.2.3 Perceptual Evaluation

Listening tests confirmed that the attribute increases indicated by the RCV scores were apparent perceptually. After biasing the speed dimension, even though outputs were much "blurrier" than the original, it was apparent that the rate of footsteps was higher than in the original clip. Interestingly, while all footsteps in the dataset the model was trained on had a consistent tempo, the same was not the case for the model's outputs when a speed bias was added. This warrants further investigation and will be analyzed in the discussion section.

In addition, upon comparing auto-encoded files with a grass bias to original files containing the attribute, it is clear that biasing the grass dimension resulted in perceptually higher quantities of said attribute in the model's outputs.

Chapter 6

Discussion

This chapter will present a discussion of the results posed in the previous chapter.

6.1 Challenges Faced

6.1.1 Posterior Collapse

Various challenges appeared during the training phase of the model. In particular, appending a discriminative block to the middle of a stable VAE proved a less-than-simple task.

Incentivizing the model to produce a disentangled latent representation required much more than simply training the discriminator in parallel. Initial training runs with the GAN added gave catastrophic results as shown in figure 6. After achieving rapidly decreasing loss and stabilization, the introduction of loss terms related to the discriminator caused model reconstructions to fail completely.

This phenomenon is commonly known as "adversarial posterior collapse". Given that disentanglement was encouraged by subtracting the discriminator's loss from the overall loss of the model (reconstruction + KL-divergence), the model essentially decided that fooling the discriminator was more important than providing faithful reconstructions in order to achieve a low overall loss. Thus, it began producing

meaningless latent codes from which the discriminator could not read and accurately predict attributes.

Fixing this required multiple steps. First, we added a weighting factor λ to the adversarial loss component. Initially this proved insufficient, so we implemented a scheduled linear ramp up to a pre-defined maximum λ term. These changes gave the encoder time to learn a robust representation and become strong enough to fool the discriminator without resorting to abandoning the task of approximating a realistic posterior distribution.

Figure 8: Loss curve during initial training with GAN reading latent codes.

Initial Lambda	Lambda Delay	Max Lambda
0.01	10000	0.5

Table 2: Parameters related to discriminator loss weight control. "Initial Lambda" refers to the initial value of the loss term weight. "Lambda Delay" refers to the amount of steps before the ramp up began. "Max Lambda" refers to the maximum weight term that was applied after the linear ramp up.

6.1.2 Inconsistent Footstep Tempo

Biasing the speed dimension resulted in a definite increase in footstep density, though the footsteps occurred at inconsistent intervals. This behavior is not necessarily expected or desired as the original dataset only contained samples with consistent, evenly-spaced intervals between events.

This phenomenon likely occurred due to the nature of the model’s latent representation. Given that the disentangled latent codes contain information about how to represent their corresponding feature, each time step in that dimension represents the quantity of that feature at that given time step.

Therefore, it might be inferred that each time step in the latent code for the speed dimension represents how many footstep events occur in that time frame. Each time frame is not long enough to fit an entire footstep event, leading to the overall "choppiness" and inconsistency of the footsteps when the speed dimension was altered.

6.2 Conclusions

The experiments demonstrated the promise of achieving controllable audio generation in an adversarially disentangled VAE framework. While initial attempts led to adversarial posterior collapse and complete reconstruction failure, careful tuning of the adversarial loss weighting through a delayed linear ramp-up ultimately stabilized training and preserved meaningful latent representations. Similarly, while biasing the speed dimension successfully increased footstep density, the resulting irregularities in tempo highlighted limitations in how temporal structure is encoded and manipulated within the latent space. These findings suggest that although it requires careful balancing of objectives, adversarial disentanglement can encourage a meaningful latent representation and controllable outputs.

6.3 Future Work

Challenges faced in achieving temporally consistent and coherent outputs indicate that a different strategy may need to be applied to time-dependent semantic features. In particular, deep-learning architectures that better account for temporal sequences such as RNNs, LSTMs, and Transformers may be better suited for this aspect. A comprehensive solution may come in the form of a hybrid VAE-RNN architecture that combines the representational power of statistical distribution modeling with the sequence modeling capabilities of recurrent neural networks.

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The full repository containing the code written for this project can be found at
<https://github.com/JedPadoa/SemanticFader>